

SECTION: BLOCKCHAIN

A STRUCTURE FOR EVALUATING THE POTENTIAL OF BLOCKCHAIN USE CASES IN FINANCE

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ABSTRACT: Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) is said to have a huge impact on the financial industry. This paper analyses the frequently mentioned use cases of DLT in the financial services industry by describing the currently established processes and its participants. It develops a structure for evaluating the potential of the DLT-based alternatives. The paper shows the advantages and limitations of blockchain applications in the different finance use cases.

JEL CLASSIFICATIONS: F33, G21, O31, O33

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1. Introduction

Over the last 50 years, information technology has been fundamental to the transformation of the financial services industry. Since the 1960s, banks have been using information technology to replace physical recordings with digital data. In the beginning, banks solely used mainframes for batch processing, which was followed by the use of terminals for interactive processing. The next step in the transformation of the financial services industry was enabled by personal computers and the connection of the distributed processing units over networks, which allowed for digital interconnection of the banking system with payment or trading facilities such as SWIFT. In addition, this technological development not only improved back office processes and interbank services, but also led to innovations improving the client interface, starting with the introduction of the Automated Teller Machine (ATM). A further milestone was the development of digital banking solutions, especially for payment and trading services, enabled by the wide dissemination of the Internet. Nowadays, almost every bank offers a digital banking solution to its clients. Additionally, the transformation of the mobile phone into a smart device made financial services accessible from anywhere and at any time (World Economic Forum, 2016).

Nowadays, different technologies drive the next waves of financial services development. One of which that has attracted a lot of attention is the Distributed

Ledger Technology (DLT), also known as Blockchain. The principal theories of DLT were first outlined in the whitepaper of the cryptocurrency Bitcoin written under the pseudonym Satoshi Nakamoto in October 2008.

At first, Bitcoin and Distributed Ledger Technology were often used as synonyms. This is incorrect, since Bitcoin, or cryptocurrencies in general, has to be regarded as one specific and first use case of DLT. Since the introduction of Bitcoin other distributed ledgers such as Ethereum have emerged. These more sophisticated types of DLT support user-defined and Turing complete state machine models which allow for much broader types of applications (Buterin, 2014; Szabo, 1997). For that reason, the general focus has continuously shifted from Bitcoin to its underlying technology. However, despite its high disruptive potential, DLT is still immature. Hence, the best use cases or killer applications have yet to be developed (Ankenbrand et al., 2016).

Based on an analysis of the current financial systems infrastructure and its participants, this paper aims to provide an evaluation of the advantages and limitations of the most promising DLT-applications in comparison to the established infrastructures and processes.

The paper is organized as follows: Chapter 2 gives an overview on the existing literature on Distributed Ledger Technology in the financial services industry. In chapter 3, the base structure of a financial system is shown, including an analysis of the relationships of its participants. Chapter 4 covers the evaluation of a selection of DLT-applications in the financial services industry. Finally, a conclusion is drawn.

2. Literature review

Distributed Ledger Technology has attracted a lot of attention in the financial services industry in the past months. There exists a vast amount of articles that accredit the potential to disrupt the established financial system to DLT. Possible applications range from distributed exchanges over alternative venture capital financing to new payment and clearing & settlement systems. (Brennan & Lunn, 2016; Citi GPS, 2016; Euro Banking Association, 2015; Micheler & von der Heyde, 2016; Morini, 2016; Peters & Panayi, 2015; World Economic Forum, 2016; Zhen et al., 2016).

From a technological point of view, Wattenhofer (2016) gives a systematic introduction to fault-tolerant distributed systems or DLT. An overview of blockchain applications in finance is provided by the World Economic Forum (2016), serving as the starting point of this paper. Their study identifies three transformative characters of DLT that allow new financial services infrastructures and processes, i.e. immutability, transparency and autonomy.

DLT has the potential to improve the efficiency of the financial system through the following levers (World Economic Forum, 2016):

- Reduction or elimination of manual efforts (for example reconciliation)
- Real time monitoring of the financial activities through the regulator
- Clearing and settlement time reduction by disintermediating third parties
- Liquidity and capital improvement due to liquidity risk reduction (DLT eliminates imbalance of information among market participants)
- Fraud minimization based on a single version of truth
- Counterparty risk reduction based on ensured execution of agreements

Many of these levers are not limited to DLT. Reduction or elimination of manual efforts, for example, is also achievable with traditional digital systems (Micheler & von der Heyde, 2016). In the following chapter only DLT specific factors are considered.

3. The financial system architecture and its participants

A financial system can be defined as “a set of markets for financial instruments, and the individuals and institutions who trade in those markets, together with the regulators and supervisors of the system.” (Howells & Bain, 2008, p.4). Figure 1 shows the different participants of the financial system and their connections.

The core function of the system is the exchange of funds, either immediately or at some point in the future. This exchange of funds can be unconditional or linked to certain conditions. An unconditional immediate exchange of funds is, for example, the payment of a bill. An unconditional future exchange is a government bond if it is assumed to be riskless. This implies that future interest payments and the repayment of the principal are guaranteed, which is rather unrealistic. Without this assumption, a bond is a future conditional exchange of funds, depending on the solvency of the bond issuer. The trade of a bond between two parties is a combination of a conditional future exchange of funds (the bond) and an unconditional immediate payment of the bond price. It can take place in two different ways.

FIGURE 1. PARTICIPANTS OF THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM AND THEIR RELATIONSHIPS

Trading parties may either trade their financial instruments, e.g. bonds and loans, with a central counterparty or they may do so bilaterally (see Figure 1). In the case of bilateral trade, the buyer or seller of an asset needs to find a counterparty with complementary trade interests of their own accord, which may be very costly and time-consuming. Under certain conditions, it may even be impossible to find an adequate buyer or financier. As depicted in Figure 1, a bank can serve as an intermediary between debtor (e.g. Institution) and creditor (e.g. individual C), even if

they have differing preferences concerning the extent, duration and risk of the desired loan or the desired amount to be invested. This brokerage function is part of the financial intermediation and the core function of banks (Casu et al., 2006).

A bank may therefore be defined as an institute that consistently grants credits and publicly receives funds (Freixas & Rochet, 2008). The intermediation between debtor and creditor hereby takes place via the bank's balance sheet. Alternatively, the link between the two parties can also be established directly via the market. This market can take different forms with varying degrees of organization. Stock exchanges, for instance, display a very high degree of organization, since both participants and the financial instruments are highly regulated. As soon as two exchange orders are compatible, the trade is executed and the post-trade process is initiated. This process includes the confirmation, as well as the exchange of the financial instruments and the agreed amount of money by both buyer and seller. The financial instruments are often deposited at a Central Securities Depository (CSD), which facilitates the exchange (World Economic Forum, 2016). Stock exchanges, CSDs and clearing houses also belong to the group of intermediaries.

Today's IT infrastructure of the financial system is distributed for reasons of geography, parallelism, reliability and availability (Wattenhofer, 2016). Every bank has its own ledger system with independent databases. To illustrate the inefficiencies of such an environment, assume that the institution in Figure 1 is a client of both, bank A and bank B. Based on the banks' independent databases, the client data in both ledgers can be inconsistent. Additionally, if both banks trade a financial instrument, directly or via the exchange, they have to make regular reconciliation in order to guarantee the consistency of the positions of the financial instrument in their own ledgers and balance sheets. Since Institutions have their own bookkeeping, they also require regular reconciliation with the banking ledger(s) of their bank(s). The bookkeeping for individuals is done by banks, because individuals, like Individual B in Figure 1, often do not maintain an individual database. Only a minority operates a private ledger system (Individual A), even if only in paper form (Individual C). Financial market infrastructure providers on the other hand have their own unique ledger systems (with some exceptions).

Based on the distributed IT infrastructure of the established financial system, the following problems arise (Morini, 2016; World Economic Forum, 2016):

- Information silos need detailed reconciliation.
- There is no single version of truth.
- Lack of transparency increases systemic and counterparty risk.

Financial market transactions base on the logic of "consensus-by-reconciliation". The proof-of-correctness or truth is only given by the counterparty. This limits the efficiency and transparency of the markets and leads to a higher level of risks (counterparty and operational) and costs than necessary (Morini, 2016).

4. Applications of DLT in finance

DLT can be categorized as a subcategory of FinTech, which is defined as „software solutions for innovative products, services, and processes in the financial industry, improving, complementing, and/or disrupting existing offerings. Hence, FinTech companies are firms whose main activities, core competencies, and/or strategic focus lie in developing those solutions.“ (Ankenbrand et al., 2017, p.3)

DLT shows the highest potential in fields that are subject to certain attributes. Some of the characteristics of high-potential DLT use cases include (World Economic Forum, 2016):

- Shared repository (i.e., information used by multiple parties)
- Multiple writers (i.e., multiple entities that modify the shared repository)
- Minimal trust (i.e., existing mistrust between entities)
- Intermediaries (i.e., existing intermediaries that enforce trust)
- Transaction dependencies (i.e., existing dependencies between entities' interactions)

Based on these characteristics, we identify the following use cases/applications for DLT in the financial services industry:

- Cryptocurrencies
- Payment systems
- Asset registers
- Clearing and settlement
- Trade finance
- Syndicated loans
- Venture Capital

In the following sections, each of these use cases/applications is analyzed according to an evaluation framework including the following factors:

- Revenue improvement
- Cost reduction
- Time reduction
- Risk reduction (operational, credit, liquidity, systemic)

Since there are different types of participants in the financial system, we distinguish between individuals/institutions, intermediaries (banks, CSD, clearing houses) and regulator/central banks in our evaluation.

Cryptocurrencies

Currencies essentially serve two functions: storing value and acting as a medium of exchange, which further implies money's function as a unit of account. For most currencies, the money supply is determined by a central bank. In fractional-reserve banking systems, commercial banks (banks A and B) also play a key role in the creation of money by granting loans (Howells & Bain, 2016).

The problems of the current system originate from the centralistic control of the money supply. Since central banks many times were not completely detached from political interests, they were often misused to print money to finance budget deficits, which in turn led to high rates of inflation and financial crises (Reinhart & Rogoff, 2009).

Cryptocurrencies are DLT-based digital currencies which could be used to replace centralized and monopolistic control of monetary authorities over money creation. Bitcoin is the leading representative as measured in market capitalization. Its first

specification and proof of concept was firstly described in the seminal work of Satoshi Nakamoto in 2008. Shortly after its publication, the Bitcoin network came into existence in January 2009. The domain bitcoin.org had already been registered back in August 2008 (Narayanan et al., 2016). Bitcoin's cryptography allows for the establishment of a distributed, decentralized and safe system (Nakamoto, 2008). Money is created by private actors (called miners) who are compensated with newly generated Bitcoins for their efforts to validate the system. Bitcoin's protocol restricts the maximum amount of issued coins to 21 million (Narayanan et al., 2016). As of the end of 2016, 16 million Bitcoins had already been generated. Based on the value of that time of close to 1'000 CHF per Bitcoin, total money supply amounted to roughly 16 billion Swiss Francs. Despite Bitcoin there are other cryptocurrencies with alternative money creation mechanisms. A cryptographic currency which would include money creation by a central bank, is also conceivable.

Cryptocurrencies themselves offer different use cases or business models. Hileman & Rauchs (2017) isolate four distinct industry-sectors, i.e. cryptocurrency exchanges, wallets, payment services and mining.

FIGURE 2. PRICE DEVELOPMENT OF BITCOIN IN USD

Source: blockchain.info

As of mid-August 2017, there exist more than thousand cryptocurrencies with a market capitalization of close to USD 140 billion. Approximately 50 percent of which is allocated to Bitcoin, followed by Ethereum and Ripple, comprising 21 and 5 percent, respectively (coinmarketcap, online). A similar situation presents itself with regard to the trade volume: Bitcoin, Ethereum and Ripple account for 39, 22 and 4 percent of the total monthly trade volume of the cryptocurrency market, that equalled the size of the total market capitalization, i.e. roughly USD 140 billion (coinmarketcap, online).

Based on their heterogeneous designs, advantages and limitations of cryptocurrencies cannot be evaluated as a universal class. However, the emergence of Bitcoin has

proven that a functioning cryptocurrency can be implemented by means of DLT. As elucidated above, Bitcoin commands a deterministic control of the money supply, which renders it completely independent. This is only a basic condition, however. The viability of a currency and ultimately the people’s trust in it is determined by further characteristics, which can be extremely diverse. Due to the diverse specifications of cryptocurrencies, the following remarks and the final evaluation focus on Bitcoin as the most important represent of cryptocurrencies.

As of mid-August 2017, Bitcoin as a payment method recorded a volume of up to 270’000 transactions per day (blockchain.info, online). For comparison, the SWIFT system processed close to 14 million payment messages per day in June 2017 (SWIFT, online). Figure 2 depicts the price development of Bitcoin in US dollars. The price development of Bitcoin questions whether or not Bitcoin will be able to comply with the value retention function that is part of its design. As of now, Bitcoin is able to meet a speculative function. In addition to the direct trading of Bitcoin, indirect trading has already been established with the emergence of the first structured products.¹

Bitcoin has virally spread out since its launch in 2009 without any central governance. The initially mentioned characteristics of a high-potential DLT use case can thus be confirmed. Table 1 shows the summarized evaluation of cryptocurrencies as a DLT use case, in which “+” reflects a positive and “-“ a negative impact. “na” signifies that the information isn’t available or not meaningful.

TABLE 1. EVALUATION OF CRYPTOCURRENCIES AS A DLT USE CASE

	Individuals/Institutions	Intermediaries	Regulators
Revenue improvement	+	+	na
Cost reduction	+	-	+
Time reduction	+	-	+
Risk reduction	+	+	+

Individuals, institutions and regulators could profit from cryptocurrencies. Also intermediaries could benefit if they are able to adapt their business models to the new reality. Otherwise they could be replaced by the new technology.

Payment systems

The influence of DLT is more obvious with regard to payment systems, which the following example will show: Individual A in Figure 1 wishes to transfer money to individual C. Individual A will consequently assign this task to his relationship bank, i.e. bank A. Bank A will then transfer the money to bank B. This process may operate via a clearing house or in the form of a SWIFT message in which case no actual money transfer occurs but merely a booking of the transaction. Bank B subsequently books the receipt on individual C’s account and sends a corresponding confirmation to individual C. This process is more complex if banks A and B do not maintain regular business relations (i.e. mutual limitations) and are not associated with the same clearing house. In that case, the banks require the assistance of a third bank (correspondent bank), which will conclude the transaction on their behalf. The

¹ For example see <https://derinet.vontobel.com/CH/EN/Product/CH0327606114>

transaction process is also more complicated if the involved individuals have not been affiliated with their respective banks until the transaction in question is supposed to occur. In that case, the AML/KYC (Anti Money Laundering/Know Your Customer) processes have to be completed before the transaction can be initiated.

The current process exhibits the following deficiencies (World Economic Forum, 2016):

- Payments are time-consuming and costly, depending on the transaction route.
- Data in the various IT-systems are often inconsistent and require different fine-tunings and adjustments.
- Banks require liquidity and equity for the execution of transactions.
- Onboarding of clients is costly and risky.

In a DLT environment, the final customers (individual A and C) have their own digital wallets, in which they receive and store their cryptographic assets. Money transactions occur in the form of a simple transfer via the DLT system, as the current example of Bitcoin demonstrates.

Hence, the advantages of a DLT-based payment system comprise:

- Reduced settlement time and costs enabled by the execution of transactions on a common database. Transactions within hours are feasible.
- Minimized error rate, since the same consistent database is used by all parties involved.
- Minimized complexity because of the disintermediation of clearing houses and correspondent banks.
- Limitations, i.e. business relations between banks, are no longer necessary.

The fact that banks are no longer required to conduct onboarding processes for costumers may be mentioned as an additional advantage. However, this payment system, analogous to Bitcoin, is subject to the same KYC/AML requirements as existing solutions (Euro Banking Association, 2015).

A DLT-based payment system conditions all transactions to occur in a cryptocurrency and that both sender and recipient have a DLT infrastructure in the form of a digital wallet. In case of a transaction with traditional currencies within the banking system, a DLT-based process is conducted as follows: Individual A places the respective order with his personal bank, ideally directly via the DLT system. If the required funds are in place, a smart contract approves the payment and automatically credits the appropriate account of individual A at bank A. Smart contracts are computer programs, which are able to automatically, safely and irrevocably execute contract terms in a DLT system. A further smart contract will then conduct the respective booking with bank B in favor of individual C. The advantages of such a process resemble the ones mentioned for the previous case, but they are less distinctive (World Economic Forum, 2016):

- Reduced settlement time and costs enabled by the execution of transactions on a common database. Transactions within hours are feasible.
- Minimized error rate, since the same consistent database is used by all parties involved.
- Minimized complexity because of the disintermediation of the clearing house and correspondent banks.

- KYC/AML may be integrated, especially if customer profiles are saved in the DLT system as well.
- Automatic compliance, since regulators have access to the system and receive an overview of the transactions, which ultimately makes the reporting by banks obsolete.

A summarized evaluation of DLT-based payment systems is given in Table 2.

TABLE 2. EVALUATION OF PAYMENT SYSTEM AS A DLT USE CASE

	Individuals/Institutions	Intermediaries	Regulators
Revenue improvement	0	-	na
Cost reduction	+	+	+
Time reduction	+	-	+
Risk reduction	+	-	+

The end-user profits from faster and cheaper payments systems because of its fully digital character. The regulator benefits from more transparency. The intermediary could get obsolete in the long run. If he manages to remain in the business, a DLT-based system could help him to reduce costs.

Asset registers

There are various types of registers at use in the financial system. Examples of such registers are land registries or the security numbering system, a database that includes all financial instruments with their respective administrative characteristics.

In Switzerland, the land registry lists properties and the respective rights and obligations according to private law (e.g. easement or mortgage rights). It is not one single directory, but consists of a journal, a main book, plans of site based on official measurements, receipts (purchase and easement agreements) and auxiliary registers (creditor and proprietor register). The Swiss land registry is structured according to properties, which means that for each property an individual land registry folio is created. Any Swiss citizen is authorized to gather information on the owner of a certain property and on the kind of easements and land charges attached to it. This also applies to most annotations. Additionally, a person who can reasonably substantiate his or her request is entitled to be granted further insight into the land registry; especially for enquiries about mortgage rights and priority notices. If someone is entitled to certain information, a land registry extract can be requested from the responsible authority (Verband Schweizerischer Grundbuchverwalter, online). Since the land registries are administered by the land registry bureaus of each individual canton, there is currently no centralized land registry that encompasses the whole of Switzerland. In some of the cantons, there is only one land registry bureau. Other cantons have land registry bureaus for each municipality or for several municipalities combined. To facilitate the information exchange between the numerous Swiss land registries the Swiss government has launched a national electronic property information system called “eGRIS” (EJPD, online).

The main disadvantage of the current land registry system in Switzerland is its decentralization. This flaw can be remedied by introducing either a DLT solution or a traditional database solution such as eGRIS. An example for a successful

implementation of DLT in the field of land registries is provided Honduras. By securing its land title records with DLT, the Central American nation has shown that the technology indeed is able to increase efficiency and reduce costs of public services. In general, DLT-based systems offer the following advantages for all kinds of asset registries:

- Possibility of multiple writing accesses.
- Trust in an operator or a notary’s office becomes obsolete.
- Reduction of complexity, since no intermediaries are involved.
- Transactions (property transactions in the case of land registries) may be processed in more efficient and inexpensive ways.

A real example for a DLT-based asset registry is the commercial register of the Canton Geneva, which currently is in a pilot phase (République et canton de Genève, online).

Table 3 concludes the advantages and limitations of DLT in the field of asset registries for the three types of the financial system’s participants.

TABLE 3. EVALUATION OF ASSET REGISTER AS A DLT USE CASE

	Individuals/Institutions	Intermediaries	Regulators
Revenue improvement	+	-	na
Cost reduction	+	+	+
Time reduction	+	+	+
Risk reduction	+	+	+

All parties benefit from the new technology in some way. Only intermediaries could lose revenues if some of their services get replaced by a DLT solution.

Clearing and settlement

The potential of DLT in the clearing and settlement process of financial instruments can again be demonstrated by means of Figure 1: Assume that Individual A wants to buy a financial instrument from individual C and that said financial instrument is listed at an exchange and stored at a central securities depository. Hence, individual A submits a buy order for the respective financial instrument to his broker (bank A). On the other side, individual C gives a sell order for the same financial instrument to his respective broker (bank B). Bank A and B then send the respective orders to the exchange. At the exchange, both orders are executed, provided that the complementary orders match. In this case, the exchange sends the respective confirmations to bank A and bank B. The banks then initiate the clearing and settlement process. The settlement (delivery) and payment instructions of the involved clients are sent to the CSD and the clearing house by the exchange first-hand, or alternatively by the banks themselves. If the information sent matches with those stored at the CSD and the clearing house, the financial instrument and the cash are simultaneously transferred from individual A to individual C (cash) and vice versa (financial instrument). Finally, both banks book the trade in their ledger and send confirmations to their clients. Note that there can be direct interfaces to asset registers such as the issuer register (Micheler & von der Heyde, 2016).

The main disadvantages of the current process are (Peters & Panayi, 2015):

- Duration between trade execution and settlement often takes three days (t+3).
- Data often is inconsistent and needs reconciliation.
- Counterparty and settlement risk between trade execution and settlement.

In a DLT environment, the process could be enhanced in the following way: The trading process would be identical because currently DLT is not capable of processing vast amounts of real-time transactions (Brennan & Lunn, 2016). DLT firstly comes into play after the matching of a trade when the exchange sends the trade confirmation to the DLT system. After the validation of the confirmation by the banks on behalf of their clients, smart contracts ensure simultaneous transfer of the financial instrument and cash between banks or clients (World Economic Forum, 2016).

The benefits of such a DLT system include (World Economic Forum, 2016):

- Reduced settlement time enabled by the execution of transactions on a common database. A reduction to a same day settlement is feasible.
- Minimized error rate, since the same consistent database is used by all parties involved.
- Minimized complexity because of the disintermediation of the clearing house and the CSD.
- Automatic compliance, since regulators have a complete overview of the system and the participating banks, so exchanges are no longer required to produce regulatory reports.

The evaluation of the advantages and limitations of DLT-based clearing and settlement systems is given in Table 4.

TABLE 4. EVALUATION OF CLEARING AND SETTLEMENT SYSTEMS AS A DLT USE CASE

	Individuals/Institutions	Intermediaries	Regulators
Revenue improvement	+	-	na
Cost reduction	+	+	+
Time reduction	+	+	+
Risk reduction	+	+	+

Clearing and settlement is evaluated similar to asset registers: All parties benefit from the efficiency gains of a DLT-based solution. However, intermediaries could lose some of their revenues if their current services get replaced.

Trade finance

The term “trade finance” designates a process, whereby a supplier and a purchaser reduce settlement risks by including a trustworthy intermediary. Banks often serve as such intermediaries. The supplier and the purchaser run the risk of their counterparty either not paying for the goods or delivering deficient goods or not delivering at all, respectively. The intermediary receives compensation for the absorption and supervision of such settlement risks. The worldwide volume of the current trade finance market adds up to USD 10 billion (World Economic Forum, 2016).

The existing process of trade finance is structured as follows: A seller and a buyer agree on the sale of a product. The buyer presents a copy of the invoice to his bank A. Bank A subsequently transfers the respective amount from the account of the buyer to a trustworthy intermediary. The intermediary informs the seller's bank of receiving the money. The seller then delivers the product. As soon as the buyer has taken delivery of the product, he informs the intermediary, which will then transfer the money to the seller (World Economic Forum, 2016).

The existing process is subject to the following deficiencies:

- The trading parties may use different forms of business documentation, which can result in errors and coordination problems.
- Payment is delayed due to long communication paths.

In a DLT system, the process is executed as follows: The seller or the buyer enters the contract and the pertaining details into the DLT system in the form of a smart contract. The counterparty then digitally signs the smart contract. The buyer's bank electronically confirms the availability of the required funds (letter of credit). Based on this information, the seller triggers the delivery of the product. The buyer or the buyer's agent then confirms the reception of the product, after which the payment is automatically initiated by the smart contract. The banks of the seller and buyer could even be made completely obsolete in the process by using a cryptocurrency as a medium of exchange (World Economic Forum, 2016).

The DLT solution leads to the following advantages (World Economic Forum, 2016):

- Reduced settlement time and costs enabled by the execution of transactions on a common database. A reduction to a same day settlement is feasible.
- Minimized error rate, since the same consistent database is used by all parties involved.
- Minimized complexity, since no intermediary is involved in the process.
- Limitations and counterparty risks are neither existent nor necessary.

A summarized evaluation of DLT in the field of trade finance is shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5. EVALUATION OF TRADE FINANCE AS A DLT USE CASE

	Individuals/Institutions	Intermediaries	Regulators
Revenue improvement	0	-	na
Cost reduction	+	+	+
Time reduction	+	+	+
Risk reduction	+	+	+

DLT leads to more efficient trade finance process with a positive impact on costs, time and risk for all groups of participants. Again, intermediaries could suffer from revenue losses due to a replacement of their current services in trade finance.

Syndicated loan

A syndicated loan is financed by multiple investors, a so-called syndicate, in which one investor or creditor assumes the leadership and administrative responsibilities. In

2014, the worldwide market volume for syndicated loans was listed at more than USD 3.5 billion (World Economic Forum, 2016).

In the classical financing process, an applicant for credit (institution in Figure 1) orders the arranger of the funding (bank B) to organize the credit relationship. This leading bank conducts a credit analysis and searches for further banks (bank A), which are willing to finance a part of the loan as a syndicate member. Additionally, bank B takes on the responsibilities of credit administration and coordination between all syndicate members.

The existing process exhibits the following deficiencies (World Economic Forum, 2016):

- The process is time-consuming and costly (search for participants, exchange of data and documents, etc.).
- Relevant data is stored in various non-integrated systems in a distributed manner.
- Payments occur manually via existing systems.
- In the case of a loan default, the proceedings are settled manually by the various participants.
- The lead manager constitutes an expensive intermediary.

The same process could be enhanced in the following way by introducing a DLT system: The credit-seeking company presents a credit application to its lead bank. The lead bank then conducts a credit- and KYC analysis of the company and publishes the respective information via the distributed system for all interested (and eligible) banks to see. The dissemination of the relevant information significantly simplifies and expedites the process of searching for syndicate members. All agreements are displayed in the form of smart contracts, which automatizes the settlement process and makes an intermediary obsolete (World Economic Forum, 2016).

With regard to syndicated loans, a DLT system has the following advantages (World Economic Forum, 2016):

- The process of finding syndicate members is simplified and expedited by a transparent data management. By recording the various selection criteria of the syndicate members, the application of smart contracts could potentially automatize this process completely.
- The analysis and the signing of the contract is simplified and expedited by consistent data storage.
- Automatic compliance, since regulators have access to the system. They receive an overview of the respective transactions, which renders the reporting of banks obsolete.
- Reduction of settlement time, costs and risks, since the process is executed on the common distributed database and automatized by using smart contracts.
- Minimized error rate due to the consistency of data storage and usage.
- Minimized complexity since no lead bank is involved in the settlement process.
- AML/KYC can be integrated, especially if customer profiles are stored in the system as well.

Table 6 shows an assessment of the advantages and limitations of a DLT system for the issuance of syndicate loans, with respect to the different system participants.

TABLE 6. EVALUATION OF SYNDICATED LOANS AS A DLT USE CASE

	Individuals/Institutions	Intermediaries	Regulators
Revenue improvement	0	-	na
Cost reduction	+	+	+
Time reduction	+	+	+
Risk reduction	+	+	+

Venture capital

The funding of startups traditionally occurs via relations (families, friends, etc.), venture capital funds, company funds or funding platforms. Startups usually try to raise funds by directly presenting their business model and business plan to potential investors. Convinced investors subsequently conduct due diligence investigations and invest in case of a positive outcome. Financing rounds usually allow a company to fund the next period of growth and generally ensure a company’s liquidity for 12 months on average. In many cases, the whole process then starts anew.

The current financing process comes with several inefficiencies:

- High search and process costs for comparatively small transaction sizes.
- No transparent secondary trading exists.
- Documentation for investor relation and due diligence are not available consistently (versions, historization, etc.).

Representing the various DLT systems that are conceptually feasible in this area, the Initial Coin Offering (ICO) will be described in the following. An ICO is a sale of a cryptocurrency, which allows speculators, supporters and investors to support blockchain projects. Cryptocurrencies, also called tokens, may be used as means of payments on the developed blockchain solutions or they may represent shares in a company. In particular, ICO tokens can serve different purposes such as an investment product, a currency or a more functional design. ICOs thus share the characteristics of crowdfunding (crowd investing and/or reward-based crowdfunding) and initial public offerings (IPO) (Ankenbrand et al., 2017).

Funding via ICOs exhibits the following advantages:

- The process of finding investors is simplified and expedited by a transparent data management. By recording the various selection criteria of the investors, the application of smart contracts could potentially automatize this process completely.
- Due diligence proceedings and transaction settlements are simplified and expedited by consistent data storage.
- Reduction of settlement time and costs, since the process is executed on a common distributed database.
- Minimized error rate due to the consistency of data storage and usage.
- AML/KYC can be integrated, especially if customer profiles are stored in the system as well.

- From the first financing round onwards, a continuous secondary market can be made available.
- Tokens or shares can be managed consistently throughout all financing rounds up to a possible IPO.

In the first half of 2017 over USD 1.2 billion were raised through ICOs, far more than venture capital investment into DLT companies. The offerings are often issued by collections of people which may or may not be organized as a legal entity. Since there is no global consensus on the regulatory status of tokens issued in ICOs, they are treated differently across jurisdictions. In some countries such as the US, ICO tokens are treated as securities, whereas other countries classify them as currencies or commodities. Ethereum is the preferred platform for ICOs due to its ERC20 token standards. ICOs launch with developed products, a clear roadmap or with a vague idea. Some ICOs are fraudulent and intend to take advantage of speculation in the ecosystem by leveraging social media promotion and lack of regulation. The rapid growth in total volume invested via ICOs in the first half of 2017 can mainly be explained by the demand of mainstream investors, the enterprise efforts in the financial industry and the speculation/diversification of the ecosystem (Sokolin, 2017).

The evaluation of venture capital as a use case of DLT is given in Table 7.

TABLE 7. EVALUATION OF VENTURE CAPITAL AS A DLT USE CASE

	Individuals/Institutions	Intermediaries	Regulators
Revenue improvement	+	-	na
Cost reduction	+	+	+
Time reduction	+	+	+
Risk reduction	+	+	0

The advantages for all stakeholders are obvious. Only intermediaries (here venture capitalist) could lose parts of their profit pools. For regulators and supervisors the missing experience could pose a potential risk.

5. Limitation of DLT in finance

The main limitation of the current DLT solutions is that they are not capable of processing large scale data. This problem is not only limited to public (or permissionless), but also to private (or permissioned) DLT systems, which typically show higher performances than their public counterparts (Dinh et.al.,2017).

There are different initiatives to improve the scalability of DLT systems. One example is the Coco framework of Microsoft which aims to overcome this limitation by approaching the throughput and latency of traditional database systems with a DLT-based environment. The throughput amounts to 1'600 transactions per second in relation to 20 transactions per second of the public Ethereum platform with a low latency of only hundreds of milliseconds in relation to around 10 to 20 seconds. (Microsoft, 2017)

Another problem arises from the missing legal enforceability of smart contracts (Peters & Panayi, 2015). One solution approach therefore is the dual integration, i.e. the linkage of real world legal contracts to smart contracts (Eris, online).

In theory, DLT is very secure. In practical applications, however, there are still different data integrity and fraud issues (Peters & Panayi, 2015).

Besides of actual technical, legal and operational limitations, networks effects are also crucial for a broad adoption of DLT systems. DLT can only tap its full potential if a critical mass of participants is achieved. This issue has already stopped innovative digital solutions in the past (Micheler & von der Heyde, 2016).

6. Conclusion

The evaluated use cases show a huge potential for DLT systems in the financial services industry. DLT enables individuals and institutions to improve their revenue and to reduce their costs, time and risks. Intermediaries can also benefit in terms of cost, time and risk reduction. However, they are suffering from losing revenues in most DLT use cases. The benefits for regulatory authorities are comparably clear. Due to the transparent nature of DLT systems, regulators are enabled to supervise the financial system's participants more efficient. The development of DLT systems in the financial services industry is expected to be of an evolutionary rather than a disruptive nature. In the end, an asset servicing layer based on a shared consensus ledger can integrate the whole lifecycle of an asset: starting with the asset creation, followed by trading, clearing and settlement, and accompanied by valuation and balancing (Euro Banking Association, 2015).

In addition to the application-oriented perspective of this paper, further economic implications result from companies in the DLT industry. Relevant indicators hereof are venture capital investments and company valuations. Potential creation of value in the form of new jobs should be kept in mind as well.

In this context, Switzerland has witnessed the emergence of the Crypto Valley. The center of Crypto Valley lies in Zug, which, by the end of 2016, hosted 10 DLT companies. 5 more DLT companies are located in the neighboring canton of Zurich. This cluster encompasses not just companies but also a lively community in the form of associations, events, educational services, and research institutions. In addition to conventional measures aimed at promoting the economy, the city of Zug also accepts Bitcoin as a payment method for charges up to CHF 200. This symbolic gesture has received a great, positive response from the international community.

DLT systems will most likely not be able to prevent the occurrence of financial crises in the future. They do, however, have the potential to increase transparency and trust in the financial system while minimizing its complexity. This could potentially reduce the impact of crises. In any case, DLT definitely has a huge potential to increase the efficiency of the financial system.

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